

Remembering My Roots: Exploring Guatemala’s Cultural Identity in Southern California

Isabel P. Martinez

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Approved by:

Dr. Paulo Simões, University Honors Program

Dr. Stacy Mallicoat, Director, University Honors Program

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Abstract

Amid political turmoil in the mid-20th century, many Guatemalan immigrant families arrived in the United States. They settled in Southern California's already-established Hispanic and Latinx communities. Their cultural identity evolved through intermingling diverse ethnicities, giving rise to a new Guatemalan American identity. An ethnographic study was conducted to discover how this new Guatemalan American cultural identity came to be. Across three generations, 11 Guatemalan or Guatemalan-heritage individuals living in Southern California, aged 2 to 48, with varied backgrounds and histories were interviewed. First-generation Guatemalan immigrants faced assimilating challenges due to language barriers and lower education levels but retained their overall cultural practices and traditions. Second-generation Guatemalans assimilated and acculturated more easily but lost much of their cultural heritage and identity. They adopted the cultural identity of their surrounding communities, such as Mexican or American culture. Upon realizing they had lost their ancestral heritage over time, third-generation Guatemalans reclaimed some of it. All generations experienced some level of discrimination when linked to their Guatemalan indigenous Mayan heritage. This type of study is essential for understanding how immigrant cultural identity evolves over generations and in a new place of settlement. It is essential to promote support for immigrant integration and cultural diversity, considering Southern California's rich multicultural group of immigrant communities. Furthermore, understanding the challenges immigrant groups face in preserving their cultural heritage can aid in promoting cultural appreciation and preservation for other minority groups such as this one.

Keywords: cultural identity, first-second-third-generation, immigrant, assimilation, language, practices, beliefs, Guatemala

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"Humble, hardworking, yet shy" are the three words used to describe the traits of the Guatemalan person by 46-year-old Juan, a Guatemalan-born first-generation immigrant living in the United States. For Juan and many other *Chapines* (Guatemalans), Guatemala is more than just a birthplace; it embodies a profound identity of culture beyond geographical borders.

Guatemalan Migration to Southern California

Historically, Guatemala has struggled with extreme poverty, political instability, internal violence, and recurring natural disasters (Chomsky, 2021; González & Juárez, 2012; González & Juárez, 2011). The Guatemalan Civil War (1960-1996) alone stands as the nation's most brutal conflict, claiming over 200,000 dead or missing. The 36-year civil war was primarily fought between the Guatemalan government and various leftist rebel groups, resulting in various human rights violations, including massacres, forced disappearances, and the displacement of hundreds of thousands of people (Chomsky, 2021) (Figures 1, 2, 3). Add successive natural disasters: *Fuego* volcanic eruptions (2018-2022), Hurricanes Mitch (1998), Stan ((2005), Agatha (2010), and the Guatemalan Earthquake of 1976. This earthquake left more than 22,700 people dead (about the seating capacity of Madison Square Garden) and 76,000 more injured (Espinoza, 1994). Internal gang wars and increasing social-political violence (November 2023 marches and demonstrations) also continue to push Guatemalans to flee the country (Pérez, 2023).

All these drive many Guatemalan citizens to seek refuge elsewhere, specifically in the United States. For many Guatemalans, like many immigrant groups before them, the United States is a symbol of sanctuary, freedom, and prosperity from the crippling poverty and violence in their homeland.

Southern California is the sought-after destination for Guatemalan immigrant groups because of its already-established Latinx and Hispanic communities. For the past 20 years, Southern California has experienced the tremendous growth of Guatemalan communities, surpassing any other place in the United States. Some places include Orange, Riverside, San Diego, and Los Angeles County. Los Angeles County stands out with the most established Guatemalan communities, fostering 177,815 Guatemalan individuals (ZipAtlas.com, 2023).

Importance of Exploring Guatemalan Cultural Identity

With Southern California having the largest concentration of immigrants globally, studying immigrant communities like this one is essential for various reasons (Americanimmigrationcouncil.org, 2023). First, we must understand the dynamics and challenges immigrant communities face daily. Understanding these dynamics and challenges can further shed light on more complex societal issues such as cultural integration, the economic impact of immigrant groups, social cohesion, and public policy. Researchers and policymakers can further develop informed strategies to address the communities' needs and promote inclusivity. Moreover, such studies foster a greater appreciation for immigrants' diversity and richness. "I have learned that I am a unique hybrid of a person. I used to struggle with knowing who and where I belonged. However, now I get to be both American and Guatemalan in my new way," stated Maria, a 28-year-old full-time college student, when asked about her identity as a Guatemalan after moving to the United States at seven years old.

Studying Central American immigrant communities, such as the Guatemalan community, can also help preserve long-lived rich traditions and customs that stem directly from the ancient Mayan civilization. With a population of 14.9 million, Guatemala is home to 24 ethnic groups; out of those, 22 are Maya, each with their Mayan language (Ki'che', Q'eqchi, Kaqchikel, Mam,

Q'anjob'al, Poqomchi, Achi, Ixil, Ch'orti, Tzu'utujil, Chuj, Akateka, Jakalteko/Popti', Poqomam, Chalchiteka, Sipakapense, Sakapulteka, Awakateka, Uspanteka, Mopan, Tektiteka, and Itzá) –a total of 6,207,503 people speaking a Mayan dialect– with Spanish being the primarily spoken language countrywide (Clearglobal.org, 2022). Unfortunately, many of these languages are being lost with time as fewer and fewer people speak and practice them.

Purpose of the Present Study

The primary purpose of this study is to explore the cultural identity of the Guatemalan community of Southern California. In this context, cultural identity refers to the community's beliefs, values, behaviors, and norms. Within these, further defining characteristics of cultural identity include the group's language(s), religion(s), nationality, ethnicity, race, education, profession, political group, social class, dress, celebrations, cuisine, art, literature, and music (Wilson, 2023). The goal is to deepen the understanding of how Guatemalan immigrants have adapted to life in a new cultural and geographical context while maintaining their cultural heritage from their homeland. The idea is to study factors influencing identity formation, community dynamics, and the challenges and opportunities Guatemalan immigrants face in their resettlement.

Personal Inspiration Behind Research

My journey as an immigrant to the United States at the age of three is the primary inspiration behind this research endeavor. Upon arrival, I encountered significant linguistic barriers, possessing only a rudimentary understanding of my native Q'anjob'al language. Struggling to communicate with peers and educators during elementary school, I faced language acquisition challenges until fourth grade, when I began to grasp English more fully. As I assimilated into American culture and language, I found myself gradually disconnecting from

my native heritage and struggling to maintain meaningful communication with my family and community.

In the years that followed, I struggled with questions of cultural identity and belonging. Misidentification as Mexican due to my physical appearance worsened this struggle despite my inability to relate fully to Mexican culture. It wasn't until my family's return trip to Guatemala during my first year of high school that I experienced a profound reconnection with my roots; a sense of belonging bloomed. However, this newfound connection brought forth internal conflict as I navigated opposing ideas of my identity in Guatemala and the United States.

My journey of self-discovery ultimately led me to embrace the complexity of my identity, recognizing the multifaceted nature of my cultural heritage encompassing Guatemalan, American and adopted Mexican influences. This reflective process prompted me to ponder whether others within the Guatemalan immigrant community faced similar identity crises, spurring my interest in exploring the dynamics of Guatemalan cultural identity within the United States through academic inquiry.

Literature Review

Guatemalan Migration to the USA

Guatemala's migration to the United States arises from a complicated web of historical reasons, notably the lengthy Guatemalan Civil War (1960-1996) and continuous socioeconomic challenges. The war disproportionately affected the indigenous Maya population, leading to higher levels of discrimination, poverty, and limited access to resources in the nation. A weak state that could not address its internal conflicts and the incentive of family reunification after many Guatemalan immigrants prolonged their stay in the United States drove migration to the United States (Jonas, 2022).

Studies on Identity Formation

Studies on identity formation among immigrant populations stress the importance of individual and collective cultures during acculturation. Immigrants naturally struggle with questions of self-identity and future courses in their new country. While current research offers insights into ethnic identity organization across individuals, it does not understand how ethnic identities develop over time and their relationship to basic attitudes and adaptations. Current research also shows that family institutions play a crucial role in laying the foundation for identity formation, yet the dynamics of ethnic identities across generations remain underexplored (Lansford et al., 2009).

Existing Research on Guatemalan Communities

Research on Guatemalan communities in Southern California is limited, with existing studies focusing mainly on migration reasons, transnationalism, discrimination, and the phenomenon of Mexicanization. Mexicanization, adopted as a survival tactic, involves adopting Mexican culture and identity to mitigate discrimination and reduce potential deportation to Mexico rather than Guatemala (Castañeda et al., 2002). While existing research provides valuable insights, significant gaps in understanding the longitudinal dynamics of identity formation across generations remain.

Research Methodology

Overview of Research Design

The research design for this study integrated multiple qualitative methods, including semi-structured interviews, primary and secondary source document analysis, scholarly sources, and an ethnographic approach, to provide a comprehensive understanding of Guatemalan identity formation outside the homeland. Semi-structured interviews captured personal narratives and

experiences of Guatemalan immigrants. Primary and secondary source document analysis examined the history and cause of Guatemalan migration while providing statistical data. The documents included community newsletters, organizational reports, government publications, media coverage reports, and photographs of events. Scholarly sources, such as books, articles, and reputable websites, provided a theoretical framework and contextual background. Finally, an ethnographic approach involved participant observation, field notes, and community engagement in social events better to understand cultural norms, practices, and social interactions. All these helped identify themes and understand Guatemalan identity, community dynamics, and culture preservation and adaptation issues in Southern California.

Description of Guatemalan Sample

The study sample consisted of individuals from three distinct regions of Guatemala: the Western Highlands, the Eastern Highlands, and Eastern Guatemala. I chose these regions to capture diverse cultural, environmental, and socioeconomic contexts, characteristic of the country's geographical and demographic diversity.

Data Collection Method

I collected data through semi-structured interviews designed to explore the experiences and perspectives of Guatemalans or individuals of Guatemalan heritage living in Southern California. I conducted the interviews in locations that ensured privacy and comfort for the participants, such as community centers and participants' homes, based on their preference, in person, via Zoom, or over the phone.

As a trained bilingual interpreter fluent in Spanish and English, I carried out each interview, which lasted approximately 45 to 60 minutes, to accommodate the language preferences of each participant.

The interview guide included open-ended questions that allowed participants to discuss their experiences in depth. Topics covered included demographic information, cultural identity, family or individual migration experiences, and social integration within the United States.

Interviews were audio-recorded with the consent of the participants. Audio recordings were then translated into English where necessary, with special care taken to maintain the integrity and meaning of the participants' responses. Participants were informed about the study's goals, the voluntary nature of their participation, their right to withdraw at any time, and measures taken to ensure confidentiality and data protection, including using pseudonyms at all times. I obtained written informed consent from all participants and secured parental consent for participants under 18.

Participants

This study included 11 participants who identified as Guatemalan or of Guatemalan heritage residing in Southern California. The participants ranged from 2 to 48 years old, encompassing a broad demographic spectrum to capture diverse perspectives and experiences. Participants were selected through community networks to ensure a representative cross-section of the Guatemalan diaspora, including both genders and various socioeconomic backgrounds. This approach aimed to deepen the understanding of this community's cultural distinctions and social dynamics. All participants provided informed consent, and I obtained parental consent for minors.

Materials

Interview materials consisted of the following key components:

1. **Interview Guide:** I developed a semi-structured interview guide to ensure consistency across interviews while allowing flexibility for participants to express their views and

share their experiences. The guide included open-ended questions exploring issues related to cultural identity, migration histories, and integration into Southern Californian society.

2. **Recording Equipment:** I used a high-quality digital audio recorder to capture all interviews. The device was selected for its reliability and ease of use to ensure precise audio quality without being intrusive during the interview process.
3. **Translation Tools:** For interviews conducted in Spanish, certified translation services were employed to ensure that translations maintained the original meaning and context of participants' responses. Translation services were critical for analyzing responses that involved delicate cultural expressions.
4. **Consent Forms:** Customized consent forms were developed in both English and Spanish to clearly communicate the study's purpose, the voluntary nature of participation, the procedures involved, rights to confidentiality, and data use.

Procedure

The ethical integrity of the research was a primary concern throughout the study. The process focused on upholding ethical guidelines for research involving human subjects, emphasizing respect for individuals, kindness, and transparency.

Informed Consent Process

Information Delivery

I provided participants with a detailed information sheet outlining the study's purpose, participation, potential risks, benefits, and measures implemented to ensure confidentiality and data protection. This sheet was available in English and Spanish to accommodate language preferences.

Voluntary Participation

I informed participants that their involvement was entirely voluntary and that they could withdraw from the study at any time without any consequences.

Consent Forms

I documented informed consent using forms written in English and Spanish. Participants indicated their agreement to participate by signing these forms. For those under the age of 18, I obtained parental consent.

Confidentiality

The study records removed or altered all identifying information to protect participant privacy. Data was stored securely, with access limited to the research team. Participants were assigned pseudonyms to keep the analysis and reporting of the data confidential.

Risk Mitigation

While the potential risks to participants were considered minimal, the possibility of emotional discomfort was acknowledged, especially when discussing personal experiences related to migration or cultural identity. I approached these topics sensitively and respectfully.

Data Handling and Reporting

I handled data with strict confidentiality. I secured audio recordings and transcripts and only used de-identified data for analysis. To ensure no participant can be directly or indirectly identified, I report results only in totality.

Feedback to Participants

As a token of appreciation and to maintain transparency, a summary of the findings will be shared with participants after the study's conclusion. This practice respects the participants' contributions and fosters ongoing trust between the community and the research team.

Identity Formation Among Guatemalan Immigrants

Generational Differences in Cultural Identity

The First-Generation Immigrant

First-generation Guatemalan immigrants in Southern California, mainly men now in their late 40s and 50s, represent a deeply heart-rending group whose life stories are woven with themes of sacrifice, hope, and cultural resilience. These men were often the pioneers of their families, departing Guatemala to escape the harsh realities of violence, poverty, and scant opportunities. They embarked on journeys to the United States fueled by the dream of better financial prospects, with the initial goal to earn enough money to support their aging parents or to build a home and perhaps purchase land back in Guatemala. Many left behind wives and children, clinging to the hope of a swift return.

However, what was intended as a temporary stay of a few months or a couple of years often stretched into a decade or more. Language barriers presented significant challenges, as many immigrants, despite having formal education and professional credentials in Guatemala, needed help to secure suitable employment in the United States. The lack of English fluency demoted them to labor-intensive roles in agriculture, construction, and other physically demanding jobs such as landscaping or warehousing. This limited their earning potential, forcing them to indefinitely extend their stay in the United States.

Amid these struggles, their attachment to their Guatemalan roots remained strong. They sought traditional foods and built communities with fellow Guatemalans to maintain a sense of belonging. This connection was further reinforced when many had no choice but to bring their families to the United States, realizing their stay would not be temporary. The arrival of their

families often strengthened their cultural practices, with spouses reinforcing traditional cuisine, dress, and language.

As their children grew up in America and assimilated into the culture and education system, the possibility of returning to Guatemala became more remote. The immigrants faced the reality that their children's futures were now tied to their new homeland, shifting their perspectives on where "home" really was. Yet, despite these shifts, they maintained a robust connection to their Guatemalan heritage. Carlos, a 47-year-old first-generation immigrant, captures this sentiment movingly, noting his original intent in migrating was because,

We needed to escape poverty and build a simple life because we live in a financial shortage in Guatemala. When my brother and I arrived, he was my father figure, brave enough to communicate with the Guëros [a person of fair or light hair or skin] and ask for work. We did all types of odd jobs to make some income and raise enough to support our family back home. Now that I have children growing up here, I realize they will go on to build their lives and get married here; they are not thinking of returning to where their mom and dad were born. As for me, I will always keep Guatemala close to my heart.

This generation of Guatemalan immigrants embodies a dual existence—struggling to integrate into American society while fervently preserving the cultural identity of their homeland. The journey of first-generation immigrants stresses a narrative of enduring cultural loyalty, adaptation, and the complexities of immigrant life in America.

The Second-Generation Immigrant

The cultural identity of second-generation Guatemalan immigrants in Southern California captures a complex interplay between adaptation and heritage preservation, differing significantly from their first-generation parents. Born and raised in the U.S., these individuals navigate their cultural landscape more fluidly, benefiting from their fluency in English and broader cultural integration. Unlike their parents, the second generation encounters fewer

barriers to assimilation, and American culture more readily embraces them. However, their connection to their Guatemalan heritage often remains indirect and somewhat weak, influenced more by their immediate surroundings than by firsthand experiences of their parent's homeland.

According to Menjívar (2002), many second-generation children have never visited Guatemala, leading to a weaker grasp of the country's cultural and linguistic aspects. Consequently, second-generation individuals often experience a detachment that leads to a fading of traditional customs, including changes in dress, cuisine preferences, and musical tastes, predominantly shaped by their current community, such as Mexican or American culture, rather than their familial ties to Guatemala.

Adding complexity to their identity, this group also experiences a phenomenon known as "Mexicanization." This process involves adopting Mexican cultural elements as a survival strategy, initially used by their parents during their migration to blend into Mexican-dominated communities to avoid deportation back to Guatemala (Castañeda, 2002). Second-generation Guatemalans sometimes adopt these Mexican cultural markers such as food, products, and social networks out of necessity.

The personal stories of young Guatemalans like Javier and Sofia illustrate the varied responses to these dynamics. Javier, a 23-year-old, recalls an instance of racism at school where a classmate derogatorily remarked, "*Mira ese Indito* [look at that little Indian]," which significantly impacted his willingness to embrace his Mayan heritage openly. Fearing further discrimination, he found it easier to adopt a Mexican identity among his peers despite the annoyance of being generalized as Mexican when Guatemalans are diverse in their own right. This experience stresses the complex layers of identity negotiation that second-generation

immigrants often face, choosing strategic ethnic presentations based on their social contexts and perceived safety.

In contrast, Sofia, aged 28, shares a more positive encounter with her identity. Although there were few Guatemalans in her local area, the Mexican community within her church embraced her Guatemalan-Mayan background. She states, "Although there were very few Guatemalans in the area at that time, the people from church, who were mainly Mexican, embraced and welcomed us with open arms. They did not discriminate against us by our different way of talking or dressing; rather, they helped us integrate into the larger community." Her experience highlights a more supportive environment where cultural distinctions are acknowledged and respected, facilitating a sense of belonging and acceptance.

These narratives demonstrate the variation in how second-generation Guatemalans navigate their identities—balancing American cultural assimilation, the predominant Mexican influences in their communities, and the echoes of their Guatemalan heritage.

The Third-Generation Immigrant

Research on third-generation immigrants is still relatively scarce, which leaves a significant gap in understanding how cultural identities evolve over generations. However, this group plays a crucial role in transforming cultural identity, forging a new and unique expression of their Guatemalan heritage. Third-generation immigrants focus on preserving the cultural identities of their parents, grandparents, and ancestors, recognizing the importance of maintaining these traditions as they become increasingly fleeting.

With legal status, rights, and greater advocacy power than their predecessors, third-generation immigrants feel safer expressing their true Guatemalan and non-indigenous identities. Their parents and grandparents diligently work to ensure they pass down this rich cultural

heritage, contributing to the emergence of a distinct Guatemalan identity in America. This new identity blends their indigenous Guatemalan roots, Spanish cultural influences, and American backgrounds.

An article by Christina Noriega highlights a powerful example of this cultural preservation, focusing on the experiences of Mayan women in Los Angeles. In the article, 26-year-old Maricela Lopez shares a powerful statement about her identity: "My ancestors, my grandparents, my parents have lived through colonization, wars, and genocide, yet here I stand wearing the one *corte* that I own, the one *corte* that my grandmother and I share; that is resilience," she writes next to a photograph of herself wearing a traditional Guatemalan skirt, known as a *corte*. "By wearing my *corte* in Los Angeles, I am telling white supremacy, 'Look at me. You tried to erase my existence, but here I am. My resilient ancestors prevailed'" (Noriega, 2018). This declaration honors her heritage and asserts her identity and resilience in facing historical and ongoing challenges to preserve a Guatemalan identity.

Linguistic Abilities

When Guatemalan families first arrive in the United States, many of them struggle to integrate into the local communities primarily due to a language barrier because most of them do not even speak Spanish. Many indigenous people have their native Mayan language. With over 1 million native speakers, K'iche' is Guatemalans' second most spoken language (Mil Milagros Inc., 2021b). Surprisingly, many immigrant homes have gone from monolingual to multilingual over generations, meaning language integration is far more complex than Spanglish. Some homes can speak up to three different languages simultaneously.

In many cases, the elders and first-generation migrants are the ones who speak their native language solely. At the same time, the following generations implement a mix of Spanish,

English, and the native language. As the line runs along those generations, we see a return to speaking only one language, with the younger and third generations reverting to speaking only English.

The humanitarian foundation of *Mil Milagros* (a Thousand Miracles) noted that the United Nations stated that "fewer and fewer children are traditionally learning indigenous languages from their parents and elders. Even when the parental generation speaks the indigenous language, they do not often pass it on to their children" (Mil Milagros Inc., 2021b). Communication is only sometimes, even within the same home.

Twenty-three-year-old Javier, a Guatemalan American identifying individual living in Southern California, stated, "I wish I knew an indigenous language. That would be pretty cool because it would help me connect better with my roots. I find it sad that there is discrimination and racism against those who are indigenous and speak a different language, even within the community."

Indeed, speaking a different language, especially an indigenously rooted one, is not always praised as a positive trait. Almost fifty percent of the interviewees reported having experienced some racism or discrimination in their lifetime, primarily due to being identified as indigenous Guatemalan.

Common Occupation Correlates with Education Level

Occupational choices among Guatemalan immigrant communities in Southern California, primarily those of first generation, are labor-intensive jobs such as landscaping, construction and maintenance, hospitality and housekeeping, farm working, nursery and greenhouses, and manufacturing and warehousing. Several interconnected factors contribute to this trend. First, limited English proficiency restricts access to jobs that require more vital communication skills.

It makes labor-intensive jobs more accessible to immigrant communities like this one, as they often require less verbal interaction. Secondly, these positions typically have lower or no educational requirements, accommodating those who may have had limited schooling in Guatemala due to their families' economic constraints. Furthermore, these jobs often do not require formal certification, advanced training, or legal residency status, which tends to be a barrier for immigrants without recognized status in the United States.

With each successive generation, there tends to be a gradual improvement in the family's educational level and socioeconomic status. Unlike their first-generation predecessors, second and third-generation immigrants are typically more integrated into American society, often born and raised in the United States, and are fluent in English. "If my brothers and I had not been forced into the labor force early on and had had the opportunity to finish higher than middle school, maybe we would have had a better life. My goal now is to give my kids the most opportunities, and I hope they know what to take from them," stated 48-year-old first-generation migrant Alejandro. The easier linguistic and cultural assimilation second and third generations obtain dramatically enhances their ability to navigate and participate more fully in American society. These generations benefit from more significant jobs, careers, and education opportunities. Second and third-generation migrants hold higher paying jobs such as office jobs, jobs in a legal setting such as legal secretaries, court reports, or compliance officers, public services and nonprofits, and professional careers often in medicine, engineering, law, education, and academia. This shift significantly contributes to the socioeconomic upliftment of their families and communities.

Cultural Practices and Identities Withstood Time

Some cultural practices and identities remain prevalent across generations in the Guatemalan community of Southern California. These include community and family values, traditional music and dance, festivals and celebrations, cultural dress, religious practices, and political affiliations.

Traditional Music, Dance, and Dress

One enduring cultural emblem is the *Marimba*, an instrument deeply rooted in Guatemalan tradition. It serves as a musical link to the homeland for first, second, and third-generation immigrants and as the focal point of social gatherings known as *Marimbas*. These events are vibrant and inclusive, where community members of all ages and backgrounds come together to celebrate life's milestones, such as birthdays, weddings, baptisms, anniversaries, and cultural and religious festivals.

At these gatherings, people prominently feature traditional Guatemalan attire. Women typically wear outfits consisting of three main handwoven pieces:

The *Huipil* (a shirt made from two sewn rectangular pieces with openings for the arms).

The *Corte* (a long-woven fabric worn as a skirt).

The *Faja* (a handwoven belt or sash that supports the *Corte*).

Each item of clothing is unique, handcrafted from cotton yarn naturally dyed using flowers, vegetables, herbs, and bark, creating vibrant, unreplicable pieces (Mil Milagros Inc., 2021a).

Men, however, have primarily transitioned from traditional attire to Western-style clothing, including boots, jeans, and silver *Charro* belts (Figure 4).

Political Affiliations

Political engagement within the Guatemalan community tends to be limited to voting rather than running for office, emphasizing a broader struggle for representation. In the United

States, among the Guatemalan community, Guatemalan activist Rigoberta Menchú is not recognized as an influential political figure but rather a pillar of cultural identity that resonates with the community. Menchú emerges only as a cultural icon, inspiring women to wear their traditional clothing with pride, much like she does at public conferences, proudly displaying a sense of heritage. “I’m going to wear my *traje*[outfit] here, like Rigoberta Menchú. At least I will wear it at home,” stated Antonia, a Mayan Guatemalan woman, when interviewed about her cultural identity (Castañeda, 2002).

On the other hand, Norma Torres, a congresswoman of Guatemalan descent, represents a rare example of political involvement. She focuses on creating a working group of Congress to become interested in Central American affairs. She believes an immigration reform is not enough; instead, the problem should be solved at its root. To her and many like-minded thinkers, it means helping poverty-stricken Central American countries due to extreme violence and, hopefully, in turn, mitigating the thousands of Central American children and adults who seek refuge in the United States from their home country (Olson, 2015).

Religious Practices

Religious practices also remain consistent across generations, with Roman Catholicism and Protestant Christianity predominating due to the historical impact of Spanish colonization. This religious adherence further ties the community to its Guatemalan roots, bridging the geographical and generational gaps that separate the immigrants from their homeland. In Guatemala and Southern California, loyal Catholic devotees practice the art of handcrafting flower carpets known as *alfombras* for the religious procession on Good Friday (Carey, 2017)

(Figure 5). The extent of *alfombra* making in the United States is smaller than in Guatemala, but the spiritual value and significance still hold high among devotees.

Identity Negotiation and Hybrid Identity Formation

Daily Type of Dress

Traditional clothes are worn less frequently daily in the United States than in Guatemala. First generations wear them more often than any other generation, especially if their profession allows them to, such as being a professional member of a *Marimba* group (Figure 6). However, the preceding generations only wear them on special occasions, such as the social gatherings of the *Marimbas*. Second and third-generation girls and women typically wear Western jeans, blouses, and sneakers daily.

Career Upward Mobility and Education Intergenerational Mobility

In the Guatemalan immigrant community in Southern California, career upward mobility and education intergenerational mobility play pivotal roles in shaping their aspirations and opportunities. Despite facing various challenges, including language barriers and limited access to resources, many Guatemalan immigrants strive for upward mobility by pursuing education and seeking better job opportunities for themselves and their families. They often succeed in various fields through hard work and determination, contributing to their community's socio-economic advancement. Moreover, education serves as a pathway for intergenerational mobility, as immigrant families prioritize their children's education, hoping to provide them with more significant opportunities and a brighter future.

Community Institutions and Support Networks

Pillars of Support: Churches, Cultural Centers, and Grassroots Organizations

Places like churches, cultural centers, and grassroots organizations support the Guatemalan community, helping it maintain its cultural identity while adapting to life in a new country.

Whether Catholic or Evangelical, religious institutions were vital for building connections and finding support in the Guatemalan community. Attending church provides a sense of belonging and community, primarily when they conduct services in the attendees' native Mayan language. Some churches even make sure the Bible is available in the language of their community. It's common to see people wearing traditional Guatemalan clothing at these religious practices, which adds to the feeling of connection to their roots.

Additionally, organizations like the Guatemalan Consulate in Los Angeles provide services and support to immigrants, bridging the gap between their home country and their new lives. Social media platforms and local publications also help keep the community informed and connected, sharing information about events and services.

Events such as the Guatemala Country Fair, Festival Chapin LA, and Guatemalan Heritage Night at Dodger's Stadium are important cultural gatherings where Guatemalans celebrate their heritage through music, food, dance, and clothing (Figure 7, 8). Even online communities, like the "Guatemalans in California" Facebook group, provide a sense of unity and togetherness, allowing people to share their experiences and support each other.

Weddings and funerals are also significant moments for community support. During weddings, the community pitches in to help prepare and celebrate with traditional clothing, rituals, and music. Similarly, during funerals, the community comes together to support the deceased's family, offering beverages, chairs, and financial support and staying with them through the night in mourning rituals like the novenarias.

These support networks help Guatemalans feel a sense of belonging in their new environment and allow them to embrace their Guatemalan heritage and American identity, as expressed by Maria, who feels she can be both multicultural and proud of her roots.

Remittances and Visits to Guatemala to Preserve Identity

Remittances and visits to Guatemala play crucial roles in preserving the identity of the Guatemalan immigrant community in Southern California. Remittances, the money sent back to family members in Guatemala, not only provide financial support but also serve as a link to their homeland, reinforcing familial ties and cultural connections. These financial transfers often support education, healthcare, and community development projects, contributing to the well-being of their loved ones back home and reinforcing their sense of identity as providers and caretakers. Additionally, visits to Guatemala offer migrants and their descendants opportunities to reconnect with their cultural heritage, traditions, and roots. These trips allow them to participate in family celebrations, religious festivals, and community events, reaffirming their identity and strengthening their bond with Guatemala despite living in a different country. Overall, remittances and visits serve as tangible expressions of cultural continuity and help maintain a strong sense of Guatemalan identity within the diaspora community in Southern California.

Conclusion

Key Findings

Key findings from the ethnographic study on the cultural identity of the Guatemalan immigrant community in Southern California reveal the dynamic evolution of cultural identity across three generations. First-generation migrants staunchly preserved their Guatemalan practices but encountered significant challenges in assimilating into American society, primarily

due to language barriers and limited access to education and legal status. This often led them to pursue labor-intensive jobs. Second-generation migrants, with better English proficiency and greater exposure to Western culture, assimilated more quickly but experienced a loss of indigenous heritage and identity. Surprisingly, the third generation embraced a hybrid identity, blending traditional Mayan heritage with their Western upbringing. However, discrimination and racism persisted across all generations, particularly concerning their Mayan indigenous roots. The Guatemalan immigrant narrative in Southern California is multifaceted, encompassing stories of resilience, cultural pride, economic challenges, and the continuous struggle for integration while preserving a rich heritage.

Implications and Suggestions for Future Research

Understanding these dynamics has significant implications for Guatemalan identity in Southern California. It underlines the complex interplay between cultural preservation, assimilation, and the community's experiences of discrimination. Future research could explore the factors influencing the retention or loss of cultural identity across generations and its impact on socioeconomic outcomes. Policy implications include initiatives to support language acquisition and educational attainment for first-generation immigrants and efforts to combat discrimination and promote cultural understanding and appreciation within the broader society.

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Appendix

Figure 1 - Husband and wife executed by the Guatemalan army on March 25, 1982.

Figure 2 - A procession making it way to cemetery Estrella Polar, Chajul to bury victims of the Covadonga massacre.

Figure 3 - Feliciano Bernal in the dug trenches of Xe'Xuxcap, Nebaj, looking for the son she lost 30 years prior.

Figure 4 - The court of a Guatemalan traditional wedding displaying women wearing traditional dress and men wearing Western-style clothing.

Figure 5 - An alfombra in Antigua, Guatemala showcasing different scenes of religious nature.

Figure 6 - International Marimba group Sonal Ko Konob' can be seen proudly sporting their traditional attire at a performance they attended on the popular TV network Univision.

Figure 7 - A group of Guatemalans holding up the National Guatemalan flag at Festival Chapin in Los Angeles, CA.

Figure 8 - 2023 Guatemalan Heritage Night at Dodger Stadium,